
Climate change impacts on hydrology and electricity production – a case study from Drammen river basin in Norway

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3 **1 Climate change impacts on hydrology and electricity production – a**
4 **2 case study from Drammen river basin in Norway**

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3 8 Climate change impacts on hydrology and electricity production – a case
4 9 study from Drammen river basin in Norway
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8 10 In this paper we have assessed how climate change might impact hydrology and
9 11 electricity production in the Drammen River basin. To assess climate change
10 12 impacts, downscaled scenarios from several combinations of GCMs, RCMs and
11 13 bias correction algorithms from both CMIP5 and CMIP6 were used by a gridded
12 14 hydrologic model (HBV) to simulate runoff for a reference period and a future
13 15 period. Thereafter the energy market model EOPS has been used to simulate
14 16 electricity production, reservoir water levels, bypass and flood flows. In
15 17 Drammen we see an increase in runoff, a reduction in the average seasonal
16 18 variation in runoff and an increase in year-to-year variability. Most of the
17 19 increase can be used for electricity production. There is an increase in flood risk
18 20 during autumn and early winter and higher drought risk during summer. The
19 21 increase in the year-to-year variability will impose new challenges for water
20 22 resources management in the Drammen river basin.
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23 23 Keywords: Climate change impacts; Hydropower; Water balance; CMIP5;
24 24 CMIP6; HBV; EOPS
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34 25 **Introduction**
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36
37 26 Globally, hydropower provides around 15% of electricity production (Wiatros-Motyka
38 27 et al., 2024) and generates more energy than all other renewables combined (IEA,
39 28 2021). As opposed to most other renewable electricity production technologies,
40 29 reservoir hydropower is both dispatchable and provides base load, two important
41 30 services in an energy system (IEA 2021). The importance of hydro power increases
42 31 with increasing share of wind and solar power in energy mix since dispatchable
43 32 electricity production is required to mitigate their intermittency (e.g. Graabak et al,
44 33 2017, Vagoni et al., 2024). A major challenge for an energy system depending on
45 34 hydropower is the mismatch in the variations in water availability (i.e. runoff) and
46 35 electricity demand. In areas with cold winters and a seasonal snow cover, the electricity
47 36 demand is the highest during winter when runoff is at the minimum. To match
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3 37 hydropower production and demand, water is stored in reservoirs across seasons and
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5 38 years and released when electricity demand is high (see e.g. Energy Facts Norway, 2026
6
7 39 that is representative for regions with seasonal snow cover). Since hydropower
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9
10 40 reservoirs can store water across season and are dispatchable, hydropower development
11
12 41 impacts the streamflow in reaches downstream water intakes. In reaches upstream the
13
14 42 outlet points of hydropower plants, the flow is reduced because the upstream flow is
15
16 43 redirected with either zero flow or a minimum flow requirement. Occasionally when
17
18 44 reservoirs are full, spill flow may arise. In the reaches located downstream the power
19
20 45 plant outlet, the streamflow follows the electricity production (Forseth and Harby,
21
22 46 2014). Another impact from hydropower development might be rapid variations in
23
24 47 streamflow due to power ramping (e.g Halleraker et al., 2022). These changes might
25
26 48 have severe effects on downstream water quality and ecosystems, and licences and
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28 49 management practises are established to mitigate these effects Forseth and Harby,
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31 50 2014).

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36 51 In Norway, the hydropower sector is a major user of the water resources and more than
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38 52 89% of the electricity production in Norway originated from hydropower in 2024
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40 53 (Statistics Norway, 2026). Other sectors in Norway that depend on fresh-water
41
42 54 resources include domestic and industrial water supply, agriculture, fish farming and
43
44 55 recreation. Additionally, both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems are sensitive to both
45
46 56 spatial and temporal variations and changes in available water resources. This strong
47
48 57 importance of hydropower in Norway contrasts with the global use of water resources
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50 58 where agriculture is responsible for 70% of freshwater withdrawals, followed by the
51
52 59 industrial (~ 20%) and domestic (~12%) sectors (UNESCO, 2024). Most large
53
54 60 reservoirs in Norway have electricity production as their main purpose (Eloranta et al,
55
56 61 2019), and the objective of hydropower reservoir management is to maximize income
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3 62 (Wolfgang et al., 2009). The day-to-day decision of reservoir release and power
4
5 63 production is based on assessments of energy prices and water availability the coming
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7 64 hours, days and season. The only constraints are requirements given in the reservoir-
8
9 65 specific licences. This is typically minimum and maximum water levels in reservoirs
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11 66 and minimum flow downstream the reservoirs (Wolfgang et al., 2009). For some
12
13 67 reservoirs, other users might extract water, e.g. for domestic and industrial water supply.
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15 68 Both low flow requirements and water extractions might depend on season.
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20 69 Both the licences for hydropower specifying seasonal minimum flows and reservoir
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22 70 water levels, and the day-to-day scheduling of power productions, are adapted to the
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24 71 current hydrological regimes, energy system and electricity demand. Towards the end of
25
26 72 this century, changes in technology, society and climate will modify both the electricity
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28 73 production and consumption. In this paper we will focus on the impacts of climate
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30 74 changes on water balance, reservoir water levels and electricity production. This
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32 75 knowledge is important for long-term planning of both water resources management
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34 76 and the electricity system.
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40 77 The most recent analysis of climate scenarios is presented in the sixth assessment report
41
42 78 of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Caretta et al., 2023). It
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44 79 shows that at a global level, climate change is expected to intensify the water cycle with
45
46 80 increased the frequency and intensity of rainfall events, accelerated melting of glaciers,
47
48 81 modified floods, droughts, groundwater storage and snowmelt patterns. Based on the
49
50 82 climate projections under a high-emission scenario (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
51
52 83 (SSP370)), Climate in Norway 2100 (CiN2100) (Dyrddal et al., 2025) provides updated
53
54 84 climate change impacts for Norway. CiN2100 shows that the temperature in Norway
55
56 85 has increased by 1.4°C since the start of the 19th century and is expected additional
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58 86 increase of 3.4 °C towards the end of the century with the highest increase during
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3 87 winter. Precipitation has increased by 21 % since 1900 and is expected to increase by
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5 88 11% towards the end of the century with the highest increase during autumn. The
6
7 89 expected outcome of these changes is an increase in evaporation and runoff by 20% and
8
9 90 10 % respectively towards the end of the century. Whereas the change in long-term
10
11 91 mean annual runoff is limited, substantial changes in the seasonal variations in runoff
12
13 92 are expected. CiN2100 show that the seasonal variation of runoff in eastern Norway
14
15 93 will shift with increasing runoff during autumn and winter and reduction in runoff
16
17 94 during summer (Dyrrdal et al, 2025).
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24 96 Previous studies show that at a global scale small changes in average hydropower
25
26 97 production are expected due to climate change (Turner et al, 2017; van Vliet et al.,
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28 98 2016). There are, however, large regional variations where Mediterranean countries and
29
30 99 central America would experience a loss in hydropower generation, while northern
31
32 100 countries and central Asia would observe an increase. Various studies have aimed at
33
34 101 estimating climate-induced changes in hydropower production in the Nordic countries
35
36 102 and Norway. Fenger (2007) shows that in the Nordic countries, climate change might
37
38 103 lead to increased runoff and thereby increased production. Increased reservoir inflow
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40 104 during winter reduces the need for storage capacity. However, changes in inter-annual
41
42 105 variations in runoff might impose new challenges, and the change in seasonality might
43
44 106 put more stress on the spillways as flood events with full reservoirs might become more
45
46 107 frequent. Similar findings are reported in more recent studies covering the Nordic
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48 108 countries (e.g. Golombek et al., 2012, Toverud, 2017). In a national study, Koestler et
49
50 109 al. (2019) highlights that the variability in winter runoff might increase as some winters
51
52 110 will be mild, while others cold and dry. This will make the long-term planning of
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54 111 hydropower production more challenging. Several studies focusing on sub-areas in
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3 112 Norway (Beisland et al., 2017a; Beisland et al., 2017b; and Koestler et al., 2019)
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5 113 confirm the findings from Fenger (2007). Beisland et al. (2017a) analyses electricity
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7 114 production in western Norway and conclude that the increase in reservoir inflow will
8
9 115 increase both electricity production and flood losses. Beisland et al. (2017b) analyses
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11 116 power production in a large river basin in south-eastern Norway. They conclude that
12
13 117 there will be large year-to-year variation in reservoir filling at the end of the century
14
15 118 when reservoirs levels will stay at a high level during wet and mild winters and emptied
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17 119 more during cold winters with little inflow. Further on, the run-of-the-river power plants
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19 120 will benefit from reduced seasonal variations in runoff as the bypass- and flood flows
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21 121 might be reduced at the annual scale.
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26 122 The literature cited above shows that for assessing the impact of climate change on
27
28 123 runoff, reservoir operations, electricity production and water availability at the river
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30 124 basin scale, a tailored modelling chain linking local climate projection to runoff and
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32 125 electricity production is needed. The studies cited above that address climate change
33
34 126 impacts on hydropower in Norway, are based on electricity production model where
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36 127 reservoirs and hydropower plants are represented. This model uses streamflow and
37
38 128 electricity prices as inputs and simulate reservoir operation and electricity production.
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42 129 The studies cited above uses streamflow simulated in a limited set of representative
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44 130 catchments. The simulated streamflow is transferred to the target catchments in the
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46 131 electricity production model. The use of representative catchments might miss-represent
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48 132 local impacts of climate change, as climate change impacts on runoff in the
49
50 133 representative and the target catchments might differ. Additionally, the use of a limited
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52 134 number of target catchments might underestimate the spatial variability in inflows to
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54 135 hydropower modules. The novelty of this paper is to establish a new modelling chain
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56 136 where hydrological models applied in each representative catchments is replaced by a
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3 137 distributed hydrological model estimated runoff in all target catchments, are not used.
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5 138 This allowed us to connect local changes in climate to changes in runoff that thereafter
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7 139 was used to simulate reservoir operations and hydropower production.
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10 140 The main objectives of this paper are to (i) develop a model chain that can be used to
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12 141 assess the effects of climate changes on hydrology and electricity production in river
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14 142 basins dominated by hydropower and (ii) use this model chain to assess the climate
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16 143 change impacts in the Drammen river basin. In particular we want to answer the
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18 144 following questions:

- 21 145 • How might climate changes influence average, seasonal- and year-to-year
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23 146 variations in water balance, reservoir inflow, power production and reservoirs
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25 147 water levels?
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27 148 • How much of the changes in energy inflow is translated to changes in power
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29 149 production?
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34 150 In the following sections we will first present the Drammen river basin and the chain of
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36 151 models and climate data repositories that we set up. Thereafter we continue to present
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38 152 results of the analysis based on the new model chain before we draw a conclusion.
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42 153 **Materials and methods**

43 44 45 154 *Study area*

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48 155 The Drammen river basin is located in south-eastern Norway and with 17114 km² it is
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50 156 the second largest river basin within Norway (Figure 1). Two of the sub-basins,
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52 157 Sperilden and Randsfjorden flow into the lake Tyrifjorden whereas Krøderen and Simoa
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54 158 joins the Drammen river between Tyrifjorden and the outlet into the sea at the city of
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56 159 Drammen. Approximately 20% of the catchment is located above 1000 m.a.s.l. (i.e.
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58 160 above the tree line) and the maximum altitude is 1933 m.a.s.l.) There are large

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3 161 gradients in climate from glaciated regions at the highest altitudes in the west (annual
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5 162 average temperatures down to $-5.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and annual precipitation up to 2350 mm) to the
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7 163 lowlands in the Southeast (with annual average temperatures above $7.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and annual
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9 164 precipitation down to 560 mm). The hydrological regime in inland and high-altitude
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11 165 areas is characterised by low flows during winter, followed by a snowmelt-driven spring
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13 166 flood. In contrast, in the coastal areas where snow accumulation and melt are of minor
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15 167 importance, the main low flow season is summer and the season with the highest runoff
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17 168 is autumn or early winter (Gottschalk et al., 1979). In-between these regimes there are
18
19 169 several transition types, depending on the importance of snow melt versus rain as the
20
21 170 key source for runoff generation.

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27 171 The main water use in the river basin is hydropower. The catchment is also an important
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29 172 source for domestic and industrial water supply, irrigation and tourism (fishing,
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31 173 boating). The catchment has 107 hydropower stations, 2 GW installed capacity and an
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33 174 annual production of 9.2 TWh.

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3 176 Figure 1: Maps of the Drammen catchment: its location in Norway and its outlet (left);
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5 177 and sub-basins with hydropower stations, reservoir, lakes and water transfers

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47 181 Figure 2: Climate in the Drammen River basin. Mean annual precipitation (a) and mean
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49 182 annual temperature (b) for the period 1991-2020 based on SeNorge data (see section
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51 183 below)

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54 184 ***Modelling chain***

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56 185 To address the research questions defined in the introduction, we set up the modelling
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58 186 chain shown in Figure 3. In a first step, the hydrological models were calibrated and
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60 187 validated using reference streamflow data. In a second step, climate scenarios were used
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189 in combination with hydrological models and reservoir models to assess the climate
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191 change impacts on hydrology and electricity production. Each element of the modelling
192
193 chain is described below.

191

192 Figure 3. Flowchart showing the modelling chain used in this study. The light beige
 193 boxes represent data repositories we used as input, the brown box a input dataset
 194 produced for this study, the dark blue boxes datasets produced and the green boxes the
 195 applied models.

196 *Meteorological grids*

197 All reference forcing datasets were provided as observational grids at a 1x1 km
 198 grid with daily time resolution. We used minimum, maximum and mean temperatures
 199 and precipitation from the seNorge2018 v20.05 dataset which is based on interpolation
 200 of observations (Lussana et al., 2019), downward short-wave radiation and relative
 201 humidity from the HySN2018v2005ERA5 dataset (Erlandsen, 1999) and wind data

202 from the KliNoGrid 16.12 dataset (Reistad et al., 2011). All data are available for the
203 period 1980 –2020.

204

205 *Streamflow observations*

206 Reference streamflow data from 11 gauging stations were used for calibration and
207 validation of the HBV model (see table 1). All stations represent natural catchments not
208 influenced by river regulations.

209 Table 1. The 11 natural catchments used for model calibration and validation in the
210 Drammen river basin.

Station ID	Name	Area (km ²)
12.70	Etna	569
12.171	Hølervatn	79.4
12.178	Eggedal	311
12.188	Langtjernbekk	4.67
12.192	Sundbyfoss	74.8
12.193	Fiskum	51.5
12.197	Grunke	185
12.207	Vinde-elv	270
12.209	Urula	554
12.212	Hangtjern	11.0
12.215	Storeskar	120

211

212 *Meteorological projections*

213 We selected climate projections from the national ensembles of climate
214 projections COR-BA-2025 dataset (Wong et al. 2025) that are freely available at the
215 Arctic Data Centre (adc.met.no). COR-BA-2025 covers all Norway and consists of high
216 resolution downscaled and bias-corrected climate projections at 1 km spatial resolution
217 and with daily time steps. COR-BA-2025 consists of climate projections for the
218 Representative Concentration Pathway 2.6 and 4.5 (RCP2.6 and RCP4.5) climate
219 scenarios from the 5th^h phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5)

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3 220 and the Shared Socio-Economic Pathway 3.7-0 (SSP370) from CMIP6. In this study,
4
5 221 we used the RCP4.5 as a medium scenario where it is assumed that the greenhouse gas
6
7 222 emissions peak around 2040 before declining resulting in a global temperature increase
8
9 223 between 3.5 °C to 4.0 °C by the end of the century. The SSP370 scenario represents a
10
11 224 relatively high emission scenario resulting in approximately 3.5 °C to 4.0 °C of global
12
13 225 warming by the end of the century.
14
15

16
17 226 For each climate scenario, climate projections from 10 combinations of Global
18
19 227 Climate Models (GCMs) and Regional Climate Models (RCMs) were available in
20
21 228 COR-BA-2025. In this study, we selected three representing the spread of climate
22
23 229 change signals between the models for the Drammen river basin. Table 2 lists the model
24
25 230 combinations used for the RCP4.5 and SSP3.7-0 scenarios, respectively.
26
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28
29 231 To address the changes on hydrology in Norway where snow accumulation and
30
31 232 snow melt are key processes, it is essential to further downscale the RCM model outputs
32
33 233 and correct the bias. COR-BA-2025 applied two bias-correction methods Empirical
34
35 234 quantile mapping EQM (Gudmunsson et al., 2012) and 3-dimensional bias correction
36
37 235 3DBC-EQM (Mehrota and Sharma, 2019) that are documented in Huang et al. (2025a).
38
39 236 The climate projections were bias corrected and downscaled to a 1x1 km grid covering
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41 237 all Norway based on the same meteorological grids used in this study as references.
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44
45 238 Figure 4 illustrates the changes in mean annual and mean monthly values for
46
47 239 precipitation and temperature based on the selected climate projections for the
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49 240 Drammen river basin. The warmest and wettest scenario is SSP3-7.0 where the EC-
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51 241 EARTH + RACMO models (SSP3-7.0) gives the largest increases. For the RCP4.5
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53 242 scenario, the CNRM+ALADIN models (RCP4.5) provide the smallest increase. The
54
55 243 changes in temperature is higher for the months December - February than for the other
56
57 244 months for two of the projections in the SSP3.7-0 scenario (Fig. 4 g-h). No seasonal
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245 patterns in changes are seen for precipitation projections (Figures 4e-f and i-j). The
 246 3DBC-EQM bias correction method alters the seasonality of the projected changes, in
 247 particular for precipitation, but it doesn't change the annual means (Fig. 4a-b). The
 248 seasonal changes are more similar across projections for the 3DBC-EQM bias
 249 correction method than the EQM method. The EQM method is therefore resulting in
 250 projections that captures the seasonal changes given by the GCM+RCM models,
 251 whereas the 3DBC-EQM method is keeping the seasonal variations from the reference
 252 period. More details about the differences between these two bias-correction methods
 253 are presented in Huang et al. (2025a).

254 Table 2 The emission scenarios, GCM and RCM combinations used with the estimated
 255 change in temperature and precipitation for the Drammen river basin at the end of the
 256 century. The climate projection datasets were extracted from the COR-BA-2025 dataset
 257 (Wong et al. 2025)

NAME	CMIP-phase	Emission scenario	GCM	GCM member	RCM	Bias correction
RCP45-1-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	EC-EARTH	r3i1p1	HIRHAM	EQM
RCP45-1-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	EC-EARTH	r3i1p1	HIRHAM	3DBC-EQM
RCP45-2-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	CNRM	r1i1p1	ALADIN	EQM
RCP45-2-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	CNRM	r1i1p1	ALADIN	3DBC-EQM
RCP45-3-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	NorESM	r1i1p1	RCA	EQM
RCP45-3-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	NorESM	r1i1p1	RCA	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-1-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	EC-EARTH	r1i1p1	RACMO	EQM
SSP370-1-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	EC-EARTH	r1i1p1	RACMO	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-2-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MIROC	r1i1p1	ICON	EQM
SSP370-2-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MIROC	r1i1p1	ICON	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-3-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MPI	r1i1p1	HCLIM	EQM
SSP370-3-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MPI	r1i1p1	HCLIM	3DBC-EQM

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259

260 Figure 4 Changes in mean annual precipitation and temperature and their seasonality for
 261 the periods 2041-2070 (left column) and 2071-2100 (right column) as compared to 1991-
 262 2020 for the climate scenarios and model combinations used in this study. Subplots a)
 263 and b) show the changes in mean annual precipitation and temperature. Changes in

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2
3 264 temperature for each month is shown in subplots c) and d) for the RCP4.5 scenario and
4
5 265 g) and h) for the SSP3-7.0 scenario. Changes in precipitation for each month are shown
6
7 266 in subplots e) and f) for the RCP4.5 scenario and in i) and j) for the SSP3-7.0 scenario.
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9 267

10 268 *Electricity prices*

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12
13 269 The electricity prices were based on long term marked analysis performed by
14
15 270 NVE in 2025 (Tveten, 2025) , and the data can be accessed at (NVE, 2026) . The prices
16
17 271 (NoK*100 /kWh in real 2023 NoK) are provided for the five price areas in Norway
18
19 272 (NO1-NO5) at an hourly time resolution for the period 1991-2020 (see Statnett, 2026)
20
21 273 for details about power marked areas)). The prices are provided for the model years
22
23 274 representing the assumed electricity power systems in 2030, 2035, 2040 and 2050 in the
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25 275 Nordic countries. The Drammen river basin has power plants in both price area NO1
26
27 276 and NO5, but EOPS does not allow several electricity prices for the same watershed.
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29 277 We therefore used prices for the area NO1 where a majority of the electricity is
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31 278 produced. Furthermore, we used data for the model year 2030 representing the smallest
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33 279 changes in the power system.
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39 280 To extend the electricity price time series from the period 1991-2020 to the period
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41 281 1960-2100, we performed a regression analysis based on the correlation between annual
42
43 282 inflow for all Norway and annual prices for NO1 for the period 1991-2020. Thereafter,
44
45 283 the electricity prices were extended back to 1960 and forward to 2100 by first stacking
46
47 284 the existing 30 years of electricity process in front of and after the period 1991-2020.
48
49 285 Thereafter, for each year, annual inflows from the RCP 8.5 scenario in Koestler, V.J. et
50
51 286 al. (2019) were used to estimate the annual price using our regression model. In a final
52
53 287 step, all electricity prices within each year were multiplied by a common factor to match
54
55 288 the estimated annual price. This approach provided us price time series with variation at
56
57 289 both sub-annual and annual time scales. We used the same price time series across all
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3 290 climate scenarios used in this study. The variation in weekly electricity prices for the
4
5 291 periods 1991-2020, 2041-2070 and 2071-2100 is shown in Figure 5. This approach
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7 292 results in similar seasonal variations in prices across periods, but with decreasing prices
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9 293 towards the end of the century.
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12 294

35 295 Figure 5. Variations in weekly electricity prices used in this study for the period 1991-
36 296 2020, 2041-2070 and 2071-2100.
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41 298 *HBV model*

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43 299 We used the gridded version of Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansmodell (HBV-model)
44 300 (Bergström, 2006) at a 1 km spatial resolution developed for Norway (Beldring et al.,
45 301 2003; Huang et al., 2019; Erlandsen et al., 2021). Each grid-cell is represented by one
46 302 soil type and is sub-divided into tiles representing different land cover classes for which
47 303 water balances is calculated. This version of the HBV model has implemented a
48 304 Penman-Monteith model for evaporation (Huang et al., 2019), and it distinguishes
49 305 subsurface parameterizations as described in Bergström (1995) for each soil type to
50 306 better account for the spatial variance on water balance. In the Drammen basin, three

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2
3 307 major soil types and 17 land cover types are classified. The model runs at a daily time
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5 308 resolution and requires daily mean, maximum and minimum air temperature,
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7 309 precipitation, shortwave incoming radiation, relative humidity and wind speed as
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9
10 310 forcing data. Static model data including vegetation characteristics, (i.e. leaf area index
11
12 311 (LAI), vegetation height, albedo, etc) are needed to calculate potential ET.

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14
15 312 The model has no routing in rivers and lakes, and total runoff from a catchment is
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17 313 calculated by aggregating runoff from all grid cells. Due to this shortcoming, the model
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19 314 was only calibrated against observed discharge for small unregulated catchments (Table
20
21 315 1) where the effects of river routing can be neglected. The calibrated parameterizations
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23 316 were then applied for the whole basin to simulate water balance at each 1km grid cell
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25 317 and discharges for small sub-basins.

30 318 *Electricity production models*

31 319 Energy inflow approach

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34 320 Calculating the change in the energy inflow for a plant or a catchment gives a simple
35
36 321 and useful estimation of how much the production is expected to change in different
37
38 322 scenarios. This estimation can be done without any hydropower scheduling and then
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40 323 compared to the production from more detailed modelling.

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42
43 324 The energy inflow (GWh /y) for a sub-catchment is the inflow volume ($M m^3/y$)
44
45 325 multiplied by the sum of the energy equivalents (kWh /m^3) of all downstream hydro
46
47 326 power plants down to the sea (Holmqvist, 2013). The energy inflow is an estimation of
48
49 327 the production potential of the runoff when neglecting losses due to environmental
50
51 328 restrictions or flooding.

52
53
54 329 Figure 6 shows a map of the energy equivalent for sub-catchments producing runoff to

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2
3 330 hydropower power plants. The energy equivalents were calculated for the maximum
4
5 331 discharge of the plants. Sub-catchments in the most upstream part of the river basin
6
7 332 have the highest energy equivalent. This spatial distribution can be explained by two
8
9 333 effects. Firstly, inflow (given in m^3/s) from headwater catchments can run through more
10
11 334 power plants than inflow from the most downstream catchments. Additionally, inflow
12
13 335 from catchments on high altitudes connected to power plants with high head, will give
14
15 336 higher energy equivalent and a higher energy inflow (given in GWh/y) than the same
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17 337 inflow (given in m^3/s) for a catchment on a lower altitude. We obtained the mean
18
19 338 annual inflow volume for each sub-catchment in Figure 6, by multiplying the catchment
20
21 339 area by the long-term mean annual runoff from the HBV model.

341 Figure 6 Map of energy equivalents for the Drammen river basin.

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5 343 *EOPS*
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8 344 EFI's Single area Power marked Simulator (EOPS) (Sintef, 2025, Wolfgang et al, 2009)
9
10 345 is used to simulate the hydropower production for single hydropower producers or
11
12 346 within sub-areas, or as in our case, for a river basin with the aim to maximize the
13
14 347 income of power production under stochastic uncertainty in prices and inflow. EOPS
15
16 348 divides the area into hydropower modules that each has an upstream sub-catchment.
17
18 349 Figure 6 shows the sub-catchments used in the Drammen river basin. Figure 7 shows
19
20 350 the elements of a standard hydropower module in the EOPS model. In a complex
21
22 351 hydropower system, there may be several reservoirs and hydropower plants in parallel
23
24 352 or in series. Each reservoir is specified by a minimum and maximum water levels and a
25
26 353 volume curve. The required minimum and maximum water levels might depend on
27
28 354 season. Inflow to the reservoirs can be either observations or simulated by a
29
30 355 hydrological model. The outflow can be flood losses when the reservoir is overtopped,
31
32 356 environmental flows and various other purposes, and production flow going through the
33
34 357 hydropower plant. Environmental flows might depend on season. There might also be
35
36 358 unregulated inflow between the reservoir and hydropower plant. When optimizing
37
38 359 power production, EOPS will respect the constraints given by the minimum and
39
40 360 maximum water levels and environmental flows and implicitly minimize flood losses.
41
42 361 In situations with limited water available, EOPS will prioritize minimum water levels
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44 362 and might break the environmental flow requirement.
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52 363 The EOPS configuration for the Drammen river Basin consists of 75 modules, of which
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54 364 43 have reservoirs and 52 power stations and was extracted from the national model
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56 365 available at NVE (2026).
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367 Figure 7: A hydropower module in the EOPS-model.

368

369 **Results**370 ***Calibration of the hydrological model HBV***

371 HBV was calibrated using the streamflow data listed in Table 1. The period 2001-2020
 372 was used for calibration and 1981-2000 for validation with the Kling-Gupta Efficiency
 373 (KGE) as the objective. The calibration focussed on six parameters related to soil and
 374 groundwater processes, which varied depending on soil type, and two parameters
 375 related to snowmelt processes, which depended on land cover type.

376 Figure 8 shows the KGE results in the calibration and validation periods. It shows that
 377 the model performs well for nine out of the 11 catchments with $KGE > 0.7$ in the
 378 calibration period. Note that the model was calibrated for all catchments simultaneously
 379 with only one parameter set, so better calibration results are expected if the model was
 380 calibrated for each catchment separately. In the validation period, the median KGE of

381 all catchments is slightly lower than the one in the calibration period, but there is no
 382 catchment with KGE less than 0.6. The better results in the validation period than in the
 383 calibration period for some catchments may be attributed to denser temperature gauging
 384 stations before 2000 that are used to in the seNorge2018 gridded data (Lussana et al.,
 385 2019).

386

387

388 Figure 8. Calibration (years 2001-2020) and validation (years 1981-2000) results for
 389 streamflow gauging stations in Drammen river basin. The KGE criterion is used for
 390 evaluation, and a value close to one indicates a good performance. Left panel:
 391 calibration and validation performance for individual streamflow stations. Right panel:
 392 box-plots showing the minimum, maximum, quartiles and median KGE values for
 393 streamflow stations in unregulated catchments.

394

395 ***Water balance projections***

396 The daily water balance was calculated for the whole period from 1991-2100 using the
397 calibrated HBV model and the in total 12 climate change projections in Table 2. Figure
398 9 below shows the estimated change in mean annual runoff and mean annual maximum
399 snow water equivalent (SWE) for the whole catchment. Two of three of the projections
400 from the SSP3-7.0 scenario show higher increase in annual runoff as compared to
401 projections from the RCP4.5 scenario for both future periods. The projections from the
402 SSP3-7.0 scenario show an increase in changes from the near future (2041-2070) to the
403 far future (2071-2100) period relative to the reference period (1991-2020), whereas
404 projections from RCP4.5 scenario are more similar across these two periods. Within
405 each scenario there is a substantial difference between projections and the projected
406 changes in mean annual runoff overlaps partially across scenarios. The projections from
407 one model used for the RCP4.5 scenario, CNRM-r1i1p1-ALADIN, gives reduction in
408 runoff in the two future periods. The changes in mean annual runoff are sensitive to
409 changes in both precipitation and temperature. Increasing temperature leads to
410 increasing evaporation due to longer snow free season and higher potential evaporation.
411 To obtain an increase in runoff, the increase in precipitation needs to be higher than
412 increase in evaporation. We see this effect for the CNRM-r1i1p1-ALADIN where we
413 see that the runoff decreases even if the precipitation increases slightly (Figure 4).

414 All scenarios and models show a decrease in mean annual maximum SWE. The smallest
415 decrease is seen for EC-EARTH- r3i1p1-HIRHAM from the RCP4.5 scenario whereas
416 the largest decrease is seen for EC-EARTH-r1i1p1-RACMO from the SSP3-7.0
417 scenario. As for mean annual runoff, changes in SWE are sensitive to changes in both
418 temperature and precipitation.

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3 419 The projected change in mean annual runoff is mainly sensitive to the combination of
4
5 420 GCMs and RCMs used and to a smaller degree the bias correction method. On the other
6
7 421 hand, the change in maximum SWE is sensitive to the bias correction method. The
8
9 422 reason is that the maximum SWE is sensitive to the seasonality of precipitation and
10
11 423 temperatures.
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32 425 Figure 9 Change in mean annual runoff and mean annual maximum SWE for the
33 426 Drammen river basin in the near future (2041-2070) and the far future (2071-2100)
34 427 period relative to the reference period (1991-2020) using climate change projections
35 428 from the RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM,
36 429 RCMs and bias correction methods.
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44 431 The variation in mean annual runoff and annual maximum SWE within each period is
45 432 shown as boxplots in Figure 10. Again, we see that mean annual runoff mainly is
46 433 sensitive to the GCM-RCM model used whereas SWE is sensitive to bias correction
47 434 method. The year-to-year variations in these variables are large and the ranges of runoff
48 435 and SWE to a large degree overlap across periods. For annual runoff using the SSP3-7.0
49 436 scenario, the wettest years get wetter in the future period whereas the dry years still
50 437 might be as dry as in the reference period. For the RCP4.5 scenario, the extreme years
51 438 are similar across the periods, whereas the bulk of the data shifts towards higher values.
52 439 For annual maximum SWE there is a systematic shift towards smaller values for both
53 440 extreme years and the bulk of the data, and the largest decrease is seen for SSP3-7.0.
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443 Figure 10 Boxplots of the mean annual runoff (top row) and annual maximum SWE for
 444 the Drammen river basin as calculated using climate change projections from the
 445 RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs
 446 and bias correction methods. The boxes represent the 25 and 75 percentiles and the
 447 whiskers the maximum and minimum values for each 30-year period.

448

449 The climate projections result in substantial changes in the seasonality of projected
 450 runoff and SWE (see Figure 11). Runoff increases during late autumn and winter
 451 whereas it decreases during the snow melt period. SWE has a lower maximum for the
 452 future periods. This is mainly explained by the increasing temperature that results in
 453 less precipitation falling as snow and snowmelt starting earlier in the year. The largest
 454 projected change in seasonality is seen for the SSP3-7.0 scenario using the EC-EARTH-
 455 r11p1-RACMO models where the maximum SWE is reduced by around 60 %, winter
 456 runoff increases by more than 100 % and maximum runoff during spring is reduced by

30 % . The bias correction method influences the seasonality of precipitation and
 temperature and therefore has a large influence on the seasonality of runoff and SWE.

459

460 In Figure 11 a) and b) we have added the simulated runoff and SWE using the observed
 461 meteorological data SeNorge2018. We see that using the 3DBC-EQM bias correction
 462 method results for all GCM-RCM models results in a better representation of the
 463 seasonality of runoff and SWE as compared to using EQM for bias correction. For the
 464 two future periods, it is not evident which of the method is the best.

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3 466 Figure 11. Mean monthly runoff (upper row) and snow water equivalent (lower row)
4 467 for the Drammen river basin in the reference (1991-2020), near future (2041-2070) and
5 468 the far future (2071-2100) periods using climate change projections from the RCP4.5
6 469 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs and bias
7 470 correction methods.
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16 472 *Electricity production scenarios*

17 18 473 *Energy inflow approach*

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21 474 The simplest assessment of future electricity production was to use the energy inflow
22 475 approach where the mean annual runoff is multiplied by an energy equivalent factor that
23 476 varies across sub-catchments (see Figure 5). In Figure 12 we show the relative change
24 477 in energy inflow using the energy inflow approach is compared with the relative change
25 478 in runoff for the whole Drammen river basin. We see these variables are highly
26 479 correlated. There are some deviations from the 1:1 line, mainly caused by spatial
27 480 gradients in runoff changes. The energy inflow approach amplifies the changes in runoff
28 481 in sub-catchments with a relative high energy equivalent. The model MIROC-r11p1-
29 482 ICON (SSP370-2 in the figure below) has the largest deviation from the 1:1 line. For
30 483 this scenario, the increase in runoff was smaller in the north-western parts with the
31 484 highest energy equivalents than in other parts of the river basin with smaller energy
32 485 equivalents. In contrast, for the CNRM-r11p1-ALADIN projection (RCP45-2 in the
33 486 figure below), we see a smaller reduction in runoff in the headwater catchments with
34 487 high energy equivalents than in the downstream areas with smaller energy equivalents.
35 488 Consequently the reduction in energy inflow is smaller than the reduction on catchment
36 489 averaged runoff.
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491 Figure 12: Change in energy inflow calculated using the energy equivalent approach
 492 versus change in mean runoff for the Drammen river catchment for the two periods
 493 2041-2070 and 2071-2100 compared to the reference period 1991-2020.

494 *EOPS model*

495 EOPS simulations were carried out for the Drammen river basin for each combination
 496 of climate projections and bias correction for the periods 1991-2020, 2041-2070 and
 497 2071-2100 by aggregating runoff simulated by the HBV model to get the inflow time
 498 series for the sub-catchments used by EOPS (See Figure 6). All inflow time-series from
 499 the climate projections were bias-corrected for the whole period 1991-2100 by a
 500 common factor to match the observed mean annual runoff for the period 1991-2020
 501 (Beldring et al., 2022). All projections of mean annual energy inflow for the period
 502 1991-2020 will therefore be similar, Start and end reservoir levels were fixed at the
 503 same level in all EOPS series simulations. We used the same time series of electricity
 504 prices for all simulations (see Figure 5).

505

506 The relative changes in energy inflow and the electricity production as calculated by the
 507 EOPS model are compared in Figure 13. The agreement between these two approaches

508 is high with some small deviations from the 1:1 line. The reason for these deviations are
 509 that the EOPS model is sensitive to several factors influencing electricity production.
 510 The most important factor that changes in inflow is distributed between production-,
 511 flood- and bypass flows. The seasonality, sequences and variability of inflow will
 512 influence how the inflow is distributed. Additionally, energy production also depends
 513 on reservoir water levels and turbine efficiency at different discharges.

514 Figure 13 Change in electricity production (%) using the energy factor approach
 515 (vertical axis) and the EOPS model (horizontal axis).
 516

517
 518 To further analyse the changes in electricity production, we extracted the flood flows,
 519 bypass flows and production flows, all expressed in GWh, and calculated the changes
 520 for the two future periods as compared to the reference period (see Figure 14). Figures
 521 13 and 14 reveals some interesting outcomes of these effects discussed above. For
 522 RCP45-2, we see a small decrease in energy inflow and a small increase in energy
 523 production (Figure 13). We find the explanation in Figure 14 where we see that a
 524 reduction in flood losses results in a net increase in electricity production. For the period
 525 2071-2100, the change in electricity production is smaller than the changes in energy
 526 inflow for all projections except RCP45-3-EQM, RCP45-2-EQM and , RCP45-2-EQM

(Figure 13). The explanation is that these for three projections, more of the change in energy inflow can be used for electricity production (Figure 14). For changes in energy inflow above 500 GWh, between 71 and 93% of the increase can be used for electricity production. For smaller changes in inflow, hydropower production might increase even if the inflow reduces (RCM45-2-3D in Figure 14) if the shift in seasonality and variability of inflow results in reduced flood flows.

Figure 14 Changes in production, bypass and flood flow (GWh) for the scenarios in this study. The number indicates the share of the change in inflow that is used for electricity production.

Figure 15 and 16 show, for the RCP4.5 and SSP7-3.0 scenarios respectively, the seasonal distribution of reservoir storage and inflow, production, flood and bypass flows (GWh). We see that the energy inflow becomes more uniformly distributed within each year with the largest increase during the autumn and winter seasons and a decrease

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3 544 during the summer. The electricity production becomes more uniformly distributed
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5 545 throughout the year as well, with the largest increase during the spring season. For the
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7 546 winter season we see an increase in the year-to-year variability of production flows. The
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9 547 reason is an increase in the variability of inflow during the winter season (the top row in
10
11 548 Figure 15 and 16), i.e. even if winters becomes milder and wetter, there are still some
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13 549 cold and dry winters in the future. The flood flows increase during autumn and winter
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15 550 and decrease during summer for some of the projections in the SSP3-7.0 scenario, and
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17 551 are higher in autumn than in spring. This indicates a higher flood risk for areas
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19 552 downstream reservoirs and a higher charge on spillways. The bypass flow increases
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21 553 particularly during winter, mainly due to the increase in winter inflow. We see also a
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23 554 clear minimum value of bypass flow that represents the minimum bypass flow required
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25 555 by the hydropower licences. The reservoir storage becomes more evenly distributed
26
27 556 throughout the year and remains at a higher level for all seasons. The reservoir levels
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29 557 are at the highest during summer and autumn. In winter, increased reservoir water level
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31 558 variations indicate that there are both cold and mild winters in the future period.
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562 Figure 15 Seasonal variations in energy inflow (a-c), production flow (d-f), flood flow
 563 (g-i), bypass flow (j-l) and reservoir storage (m-o) for the reference period (left), the
 564 near future (center) and far future (right) periods for the RCP4.5 scenario. The bars
 565 represent the minimum and maximum values for each projection in each of the 30-year

566 periods. The black horizontal lines represent the mean values and the grey lines
 567 represent the 10 and 90 percentiles.

568
 569 Figure 16 Seasonal variations in energy inflow (a-c) production flow (d-f), flood flow
 570 (g-i), bypass flow (j-l) and reservoir storage (m-o) for the reference period (left), the
 571 near future (center) and far future (right) periods for the SSP3-7.0 scenario. The bars

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3 572 represent the minimum and maximum values for each projection in each of the 30-year
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5 573 periods. The black horizontal lines represent the mean values and the grey lines
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7 574 represent the 10 and 90% quantiles.
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11 575 **Discussion**

14 576 *Model chain*

16 577 In this paper we have established a new modelling chain that is able to assess the
18 578 climate change impacts on hydrology, power production and reservoir water levels. The
20 579 model chain is based on a distributed hydrological model that simulates water balance
22 580 for the whole Drammen river basin and provides runoff from all subbasins used in the
24 581 energy system model EOPS. EOPS is a flexible model that adapt the reservoir
26 582 management to the available water resources the electricity prices. The results presented
28 583 in this paper depends on several critical assumptions and simplifications that we
30 584 summarize below.
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36 585 Modelling the effect of climate change on hydrology is challenging as using bias
38 586 correction methods is necessary to avoid local biases in temperature and precipitation.
40 587 Bias correction methods are known to disrupt the physical reality of the weather as well
42 588 as temporal, spatial and inter-variable dependencies. Nevertheless, this is required and
44 589 developing new bias correction methods is an active research topic.
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48 590 We used only one hydrological model and did not account for changes in land cover or
50 591 land use. We believe that these effects land use and land cover changes are of
52 592 secondary importance at the river basin scale as only 2.6 % of the catchment area is
54 593 covered by agricultural lands and less than 1 % if the surface is urbanized. Around 36 %
56 594 of the catchment is covered by forests and increase in forested areas due to increasing
58 595 temperatures or change in grazing practices might have an impact. This assumption is

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3 596 confirmed in Huang et al. (2025b) where it is shown that climate change is the primary
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5 597 driver of hydrological change in the future, whereas forest growth was a minor driver
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7 598 that might contribute to decreasing floods and aggravated low flows.
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11 599 To model future electricity production, EOPS needs electricity prices. We used fixed
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13 600 time series of power prices across all scenarios as this allowed us to address the effects
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15 601 of climate change alone. We acknowledge that the electricity prices are strongly
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17 602 connected to climate and water availability, as well as changes in power systems,
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19 603 production-, and storage technologies. Modelling these factors is challenging and is out
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21 604 of the scope of this paper.
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26 605 *Climate change impacts*

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28 606 The results presented in this paper indicate that the impact of climate change on runoff
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30 607 is an increase in both mean annual runoff and year-to-year variability in runoff, and a
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32 608 decrease in seasonal variations. The changes in seasonal variations in runoff is strongly
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34 609 linked to the decrease in annual maximum SWE mainly explained by increase in
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36 610 temperature.
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40 611 As expected, the projected changes depend on the emission scenario. The projections
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42 612 from the RCP4.5 scenario indicate small changes from the near future (2041-2070) to
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44 613 the far future (2071-2100) periods whereas for the SSP3-7.0 the changes amplify from
45
46 614 the near (2041-2070) to the far future (2071-2100) period. This is well aligned with
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48 615 results presented in Dyrrdal et al. (2025) and the design of these two scenarios. The
49
50 616 RCP4.5 represents a medium emission scenario where it is assumed that the greenhouse
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52 617 gas emissions peak around 2040 before declining, whereas the SSP3-7.0 scenario
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54 618 represents a relatively high emission scenario where the emission increases all the way
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56 619 towards the end of this century.
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3 620 The physical processes behind the changes in runoff and SWE are well understood. For
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5 621 the Drammen river basin, where the seasonal snow accumulation and snow melt
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7 622 processes have a large influence on runoff, changes in both precipitation and
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9 623 temperature impact both long term mean and seasonality of runoff. Increase in
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11 624 precipitation will, if temperature does not change, result in an increase in runoff as the
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13 625 evaporation is rarely water limited in this climate. Increase in temperature will influence
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15 626 the evaporation due to a longer snow free season and a higher potential evaporation.
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17 627 The balance between changes in precipitation and evapotranspiration decides if the
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19 628 future runoff increases or decreases. Amongst the 12 projections used in this study,
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21 629 runoff decreases most with the CNRM-ALADIN model. This model combination gives
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23 630 a slight increase in precipitation and a more pronounced increase in temperature,
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25 631 resulting in decreased runoff.
26
27 632 The year-to-year variation in runoff is large, and the results presented here show that
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29 633 even if the long term mean value changes, we still might see years that are as dry as in
30
31 634 the current period. In the far future period (2071-2100) for the SSP7.0 scenario, we see
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33 635 an increase in year-to-year variability in runoff.
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35 636 The change in the seasonality in runoff is mainly controlled by temperature as
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37 637 increasing temperature influences snow accumulation and snowmelt, and thereby the
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39 638 seasonality of runoff with increasing runoff during autumn and winter and decreasing
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41 639 runoff during summer. This seasonal shift in runoff is the most important climate
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43 640 change impact on hydrology in Norway (Dyrddal et al, 2025) and is confirmed in this
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45 641 study.
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49 643 The change in runoff translates into changes in electricity production. The energy
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51 644 equivalent approach provides an approximate and robust estimate of changes in future
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3 645 electricity production at annual time scales. For the near future period (2041-2070) with
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5 646 small changes in streamflow seasonality, the energy equivalent approaches and the
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7 647 EOPS model provided similar estimates of changes in electricity production. For the far
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9 648 future period (2071-2100) the two approaches give slightly different results. The reason
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11 649 is that the EOPS model, in addition to long term average runoff, is sensitive to the
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14 650 temporal variability and seasonality of runoff.

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17 651 The EOPS model provides more detailed results than the energy equivalent method
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19 652 including seasonality of reservoir storage, electricity production, bypass and flood
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21 653 flows. The results from the EOPS model shows that not all the increase in runoff can be
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23 654 used for power production, and flood and bypass flows increase for most projections
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25 655 used in this paper. This is well aligned with results from previous studies in Norway
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27 656 (Beisland et al., 2017a; Beisland et al., 2017b; and Koestler et al., 2019).

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33 658 The results shown in this paper illustrate potential future challenges for water resources
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35 659 management. There is an increased flood risk in late autumn and early winter when
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37 660 reservoirs are full and there are limited possibilities to reduce floods. Improved short-
38
39 661 range and sub-seasonal forecast would be useful to mitigate this risk. The sum of bypass
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41 662 and flood flows decreases during summer, indicating an increased risk of drought events
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43 663 during summer when the ecosystems are active. Regulations for reservoir management
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45 664 during dry events, when it is not possible to meet all minimum flow and -reservoir
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47 665 water level requirements in the licences, is missing in the Drammen river basin. These
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49 666 could help to mitigate the impacts of such drought events. The combination of an
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51 667 increase in year-to-year variability and a decrease in average seasonal variations in
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53 668 reservoir inflows makes the operation of reservoirs even more challenging as it becomes
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55 669 more important to account for the possibility for both wet and dry years. The long term
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3 670 management of hydropower reservoirs, i.e. up to five years ahead, are today mainly
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5 671 based on statistics of past observations of runoff. A more robust management would
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7 672 benefit from decadal ensemble predictions that better represents the possible outcomes
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10 673 of runoff for the coming years.

13 674 **Conclusion**

16 675 In this study we established a new model chain that enabled us to assess the effects of
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18 676 climate change on hydrology and energy production. We used climate projections from
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20 677 the Norwegian climate service center as forcing to the distributed hydrological model
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22 678 HBV on a 1x1 km grid. Sub-catchment runoff from HBV was used as inflow to
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24 679 hydropower modules in the EOPS model. Based on these inflow data and time series of
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26 680 electricity prices, EOPS simulated hydropower production, including bypass- and flood
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28 681 flows and reservoir water levels. The novelty of this model chain was to establish direct
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30 682 and consistent links from climate projections to electricity production by utilizing a
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32 683 gridded hydrological model simulating inflow for all sub-catchments yielding reservoir
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34 684 inflow.

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36 685 The results show that climate change impacts on reservoir inflows and power
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38 686 production depend on emission scenario, the combination of GCM and RCM and the
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40 687 bias correction method used to create the meteorological projections. In general, we see
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42 688 an increase in year-to-year variability in runoff and power production. At the same time
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44 689 the mean seasonal variations reduce. A model chain that explicitly addresses the
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46 690 variability at different time scales is needed to grasp the effects of such changes.

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48 691 The changes in average, seasonal- and year-to-year variations in water balance can be
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50 692 summarized as follows

- 51 693 • All climate projections show an increase in annual temperature and

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3 694 precipitation. The hydrological projections show increased runoff for 11 of 12
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5 695 projections and a decrease in snow water equivalent for all projections. There is
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7 696 a change in variability in annual runoff for the future periods where dry years
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9 697 might be as dry as in the reference period whereas the wettest years get wetter.
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13 698 • All projections show a change in the seasonality of runoff with more runoff
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15 699 during autumn and winter and less during summer. Furthermore, all projections
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17 700 show changes in SWE seasonality with lower SWE in most months.
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21 701 • The highest emission scenario we used, SSP3.7-0, results in the largest changes
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23 702 in runoff from the period 2041-2070 to 2071-2100 whereas the RCP4.5 scenario
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25 703 results in smaller changes in runoff to the period 2041-2070 and decreasing
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27 704 changes from the period 2041-2070 to 2071-2100

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31 705 The changes in average, seasonal- and year-to-year variations electricity production
32
33 706 and reservoir water level and future flood and drought risk can be summarized as
34
35 707 follows.

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37
38 708 • Climate projections with substantial increase in runoff leads to an increase in
39
40 709 electricity production. Between 71% and 93 % of the increase in runoff can be
41
42 710 used for power production.
43
44 711 • For climate projections with smaller changes in runoff, electricity production
45
46 712 might increase slightly even if the runoff decreases slightly. The reason is that
47
48 713 flood losses might decrease.
49
50 714 • The seasonality of the electricity production becomes less pronounced in the
51
52 715 future periods.
53
54 716 • The flood flows increase in particular during autumn and winter and decreases
55
56 717 during spring. The Bypass flows increase in particular during winter and spring

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3 718 seasons. During summer season the bypass flow decreases for several of the
4
5 719 projections. This indicates increase in flood risk in late autumn and winter and
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7 720 increase in drought risk during summer.
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9
10 721 • The reservoir storage changes with higher reservoir storage during autumn and
11
12 722 winter. The year -to-year variability in reservoir storage during winter increases.
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14 723 During single years, the reservoirs storage during winter are still needed.
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16 724
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18
19 725 These results implicates that energy production and reservoir management face new
20
21 726 challenges in a future climate where it becomes more important to account for the
22
23 727 possibility for both dry and wet years and increase in both flood and drought risk.
24
25
26 728 Changes in licenses for the reservoir management and improved decadal ensemble
27
28 729 forecasts could be used to address these challenges.
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31

32 **Authors Contribution**

33
34 731 K.E., S.H., T.J.H., E.G., C.A.V. and N.A conducted the research and designed
35
36 732 the methodology. E.G., S.H. and C.A.V. collected the data. S.H. calibrated and provided
37
38 733 the results for the HBV model. C.A.V. provided the results from the EOPS model. N.A.
39
40 734 and K.E. developed model code for analyzing the results. K.E. wrote the paper. E.G.,
41
42 735 T.J.H., S.H., and C.A.V. revised the paper. All authors read and approved the final
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44 736 manuscript.
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8
9
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17
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40 756 **Disclosure statement**

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42 757 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).
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48 759 **Data availability statement**

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50 760 All data will be made available upon request to the corresponding author.
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56 762 **References**

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3 945 Figure 1: Maps of the Drammen catchment: its location in Norway and its outlet (left);
4 and sub-basins with hydropower stations, reservoir, lakes and water transfers
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10 948 Figure 2: Climate in the Drammen River basin. Mean annual precipitation (a) and mean
11 949 annual temperature (b) for the period 1991-2020 based on SeNorge data (see section
12 below)
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17 952 Figure 3. Flowchart showing the modelling chain used in this study. The light beige
18 boxes represent data repositories we used as input, the brown box a input dataset
19 953 produced for this study, the dark blue boxes datasets produced and the green boxes the
20 954 applied models.
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30 957 Figure 4 Changes in mean annual precipitation and temperature and their seasonality for
31 958 the periods 2041-2070 (let column) and 2071-2100 (right column) as compared to 1991-
32 959 2020 for the climate scenarios and model combinations used in this study. Subplots a)
33 960 and b) show the changes in mean annual precipitation and temperature. Changes in
34 961 temperature for each month is shown in subplots c) and d) for the RCP4.5 scenario and
35 962 g) and h) for the SSP3-7.0 scenario. Changes in precipitation for each month are shown
36 963 in subplots e) and f) for the RCP4.5 scenario and in i) and j) for the SSP3-7.0 scenario.
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44 965 Figure 5. Variations in weekly electricity prices used in this study for the period 1991-
45 966 2020, 2041-2070 and 2071-2100.
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51 968 Figure 6 Map of energy equivalentents for the Drammen river basin.
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56 970 Figure 7: A hydropower module in the EOPS-model.
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3 972 Figure 8. Calibration (years 2001-2020) and validation (years 1981-2000) results for
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5 973 streamflow gauging stations in Drammen river basin. The KGE criterion is used for
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7 974 evaluation, and a value close to one indicates a good performance. Left panel:
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10 975 calibration and validation performance for individual streamflow stations. Right panel:
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12 976 box-plots showing the minimum, maximum, quartiles and median KGE values for
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14 977 streamflow stations in unregulated catchments.
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18 978 Figure 9 Change in mean annual runoff and mean annual maximum SWE for the
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20 979 Drammen river basin in the near future (2041-2070) and the far future (2071-2100)
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22 980 period relative to the reference period (1991-2020) using climate change projections
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24 981 from the RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM,
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26 982 RCMs and bias correction methods.
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30 984 Figure 10 Boxplots of the mean annual runoff (top row) and annual maximum SWE for
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32 985 the Drammen river basin as calculated using climate change projections from the
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34 986 RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs
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36 987 and bias correction methods. The boxes represent the 25 and 75 percentiles and the
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38 988 whiskers the maximum and minimum values for each 30-year period.
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42 990 Figure 11. Mean monthly runoff (upper row) and snow water equivalent (lower row)
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44 991 for the Drammen river basin in the reference (1991-2020), near future (2041-2070) and
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46 992 the far future (2071-2100) periods using climate change projections from the RCP4.5
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48 993 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs and bias
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50 994 correction methods.
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54 996 Figure 12: Change in energy inflow calculated using the energy equivalent approach
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56 997 versus change in mean runoff for the Drammen river catchment for the two periods
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58 998 2041-2070 and 2071-2100 compared to the reference period 1991-2020.
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3 1000 Figure 13 Change in electricity production (%) using the energy factor approach
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5 1001 (vertical axis) and the EOPS model (horizontal axis).
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7 1002 Figure 14 Changes in production, bypass and flood flow (GWh) for the scenarios in this
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9 1003 study. The number indicates the share of the change in inflow that is used for electricity
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11 1004 production.
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13 1005
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15 1006 Figure 15 Seasonal variations in energy inflow (a-c), production flow (d-f), flood flow
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17 1007 (g-i), bypass flow (j-l) and reservoir storage (m-o) for the reference period (left), the
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19 1008 near future (center) and far future (right) periods for the RCP4.5 scenario. The bars
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21 1009 represent the minimum and maximum values for each projection in each of the 30-year
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23 1010 periods. The black horizontal lines represent the mean values and the grey lines
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25 1011 represent the 10 and 90 percentiles.
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27 1012
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29 1013 Figure 16 Seasonal variations in energy inflow (a-c) production flow (d-f), flood flow
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31 1014 (g-i), bypass flow (j-l) and reservoir storage (m-o) for the reference period (left), the
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33 1015 near future (center) and far future (right) periods for the SSP3-7.0 scenario. The bars
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35 1016 represent the minimum and maximum values for each projection in each of the 30-year
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37 1017 periods. The black horizontal lines represent the mean values and the grey lines
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39 1018 represent the 10 and 90% quantiles.
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1027 Table 1. The 11 natural catchments used for model calibration and validation in the
 1028 Drammen river basin.

Station ID	Name	Area (km ²)
12.70	Etna	569
12.171	Hølervatn	79.4
12.178	Eggedal	311
12.188	Langtjernbekk	4.67
12.192	Sundbyfoss	74.8
12.193	Fiskum	51.5
12.197	Grunke	185
12.207	Vinde-elv	270
12.209	Urula	554
12.212	Hangtjern	11.0
12.215	Storeskar	120

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3 1032 Table 2 The emission scenarios, GCM and RCM combinations used with the estimated
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5 1033 change in temperature and precipitation for the Drammen river basin at the end of the
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7 1034 century. The climate projection datasets were extracted from the COR-BA-2025 dataset
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9 1035 (Wong et al. 2025)

NAME	CMIP-phase	Emission scenario	GCM	GCM member	RCM	Bias correction
RCP45-1-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	EC-EARTH	r3i1p1	HIRHAM	EQM
RCP45-1-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	EC-EARTH	r3i1p1	HIRHAM	3DBC-EQM
RCP45-2-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	CNRM	r1i1p1	ALADIN	EQM
RCP45-2-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	CNRM	r1i1p1	ALADIN	3DBC-EQM
RCP45-3-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	NorESM	r1i1p1	RCA	EQM
RCP45-3-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	NorESM	r1i1p1	RCA	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-1-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	EC-EARTH	r1i1p1	RACMO	EQM
SSP370-1-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	EC-EARTH	r1i1p1	RACMO	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-2-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MIROC	r1i1p1	ICON	EQM
SSP370-2-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MIROC	r1i1p1	ICON	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-3-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MPI	r1i1p1	HCLIM	EQM
SSP370-3-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MPI	r1i1p1	HCLIM	3DBC-EQM

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Figure 1: Maps of the Drammen catchment: its location in Norway and its outlet (left); and sub-basins with hydropower stations, reservoir, lakes and water transfers

383x240mm (59 x 59 DPI)

Figure 2: Climate in the Drammen River basin. Mean annual precipitation (a) and mean annual temperature (b) for the period 1991-2020 based on SeNorge data (see section below)

273x183mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 3. Flowchart showing the modelling chain used in this study. The light beige boxes represent data repositories we used as input, the brown box a input dataset produced for this study, the dark blue boxes datasets produced and the green boxes the applied models.

249x338mm (59 x 59 DPI)

Figure 4 Changes in mean annual precipitation and temperature and their seasonality for the periods 2041-2070 (left column) and 2071-2100 (right column) as compared to 1991-2020 for the climate scenarios and model combinations used in this study. Subplots a) and b) show the changes in mean annual precipitation and temperature. Changes in temperature for each month is shown in subplots c) and d) for the RCP4.5 scenario and g) and h) for the SSP3-7.0 scenario. Changes in precipitation for each month are shown in subplots e) and f) for the RCP4.5 scenario and in i) and j) for the SSP3-7.0 scenario.

343x473mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 5. Variations in weekly electricity prices used in this study for the period 1991-2020, 2041-2070 and 2071-2100.

651x390mm (39 x 39 DPI)

Figure 6 Map of energy equivalents for the Drammen river basin.

233x228mm (72 x 72 DPI)

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Figure 7: A hydropower module in the EOPS-model.

146x221mm (38 x 38 DPI)

Figure 8. Calibration (years 2001-2020) and validation (years 1981-2000) results for streamflow gauging stations in Drammen river basin. The KGE criterion is used for evaluation, and a value close to one indicates a good performance. Left panel: calibration and validation performance for individual streamflow stations. Right panel: box-plots showing the minimum, maximum, quartiles and median KGE values for streamflow stations in unregulated catchments.

450x296mm (39 x 39 DPI)

Figure 9 Change in mean annual runoff and mean annual maximum SWE for the Drammen river basin in the near future (2041-2070) and the far future (2071-2100) period relative to the reference period (1991-2020) using climate change projections from the RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs and bias correction methods.

343x154mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 10 Boxplots of the mean annual runoff (top row) and annual maximum SWE for the Drammen river basin as calculated using climate change projections from the RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs and bias correction methods. The boxes represent the 25 and 75 percentiles and the whiskers the maximum and minimum values for each 30-year period.

422x266mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 11. Mean monthly runoff (upper row) and snow water equivalent (lower row) for the Drammen river basin in the reference (1991-2020), near future (2041-2070) and the far future (2071-2100) periods using climate change projections from the RCP4.5 and SSP3-7.0 emission scenarios and different combinations of GCM, RCMs and bias correction methods.

649x693mm (38 x 38 DPI)

Figure 12: Change in energy inflow calculated using the energy equivalent approach versus change in mean runoff for the Drammen river catchment for the two periods 2041-2070 and 2071-2100 compared to the reference period 1991-2020.

341x154mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 13 Change in electricity production (%) using the energy factor approach (vertical axis) and the EOPS model (horizontal axis).

646x292mm (38 x 38 DPI)

Figure 14 Changes in production, bypass and flood flow (GWh) for the scenarios in this study. The number indicates the share of the change in inflow that is used for electricity production.

552x308mm (38 x 38 DPI)

Figure 15 Seasonal variations in energy inflow (a-c), production flow (d-f), flood flow (g-i), bypass flow (j-l) and reservoir storage (m-o) for the reference period (left), the near future (center) and far future (right) periods for the RCP4.5 scenario. The bars represent the minimum and maximum values for each projection in each of the 30-year periods. The black horizontal lines represent the mean values and the grey lines represent the 10 and 90 percentiles.

299x391mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 16 Seasonal variations in energy inflow (a-c) production flow (d-f), flood flow (g-i), bypass flow (j-l) and reservoir storage (m-o) for the reference period (left), the near future (center) and far future (right) periods for the SSP3-7.0 scenario. The bars represent the minimum and maximum values for each projection in each of the 30-year periods. The black horizontal lines represent the mean values and the grey lines represent the 10 and 90% quantiles.

302x391mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Table 1. The 11 natural catchments used for model calibration and validation in the Drammen river basin.

Station ID	Name	Area (km²)
12.70	Etna	569
12.171	Hølervatn	79.4
12.178	Eggedal	311
12.188	Langtjernbekk	4.67
12.192	Sundbyfoss	74.8
12.193	Fiskum	51.5
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12.212	Hangtjern	11.0
12.215	Storeskar	120

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Table 2 The emission scenarios, GCM and RCM combinations used with the estimated change in temperature and precipitation for the Drammen river basin at the end of the century. The climate projection datasets were extracted from the COR-BA-2025 dataset (Wong et al. 2025)

NAME	CMIP-phase	Emission scenario	GCM	GCM member	RCM	Bias correction
RCP45-1-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	EC-EARTH	r3i1p1	HIRHAM	EQM
RCP45-1-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	EC-EARTH	r3i1p1	HIRHAM	3DBC-EQM
RCP45-2-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	CNRM	r1i1p1	ALADIN	EQM
RCP45-2-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	CNRM	r1i1p1	ALADIN	3DBC-EQM
RCP45-3-EQM	CMIP5	RCP4.5	NorESM	r1i1p1	RCA	EQM
RCP45-3-3D	CMIP5	RCP4.5	NorESM	r1i1p1	RCA	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-1-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	EC-EARTH	r1i1p1	RACMO	EQM
SSP370-1-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	EC-EARTH	r1i1p1	RACMO	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-2-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MIROC	r1i1p1	ICON	EQM
SSP370-2-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MIROC	r1i1p1	ICON	3DBC-EQM
SSP370-3-EQM	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MPI	r1i1p1	HCLIM	EQM
SSP370-3-3D	CMIP6	SSP3-7.0	MPI	r1i1p1	HCLIM	3DBC-EQM